

SUPERPLASTIC DEFORMATION MECHANISMS OF SIC WHISKER AND PARTICULATE REINFORCED ALUMINIUM COMPOSITES

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SUMMARY: Although in the past decades there have been many investigations on high-strain-rate superplasticity of discontinuous metal matrix composites, their deformation mechanisms have not yet been fully understood clearly. In the present paper, high-strain-rate superplastic behavior of 6061/SiC_w and 8090/SiC_p aluminum composites was investigated and compared. It was found that a maximum elongation of 440 % was obtained for the 6061/SiC_w aluminium composite at $1.7 \times 10^{-1} \text{ s}^{-1}$ and at 873 K which is just slightly above its solidus temperature. A maximum elongation of 300 % was obtained for the 8090/SiC_p aluminum composite at $1.83 \times 10^{-1} \text{ s}^{-1}$ and at 848 K which is just slightly above its solidus temperature. It was considered that dislocation climb/glide was the major accommodation mechanism for the 6061/SiC_w aluminum composites. However, grain boundary sliding and interfacial sliding accommodated by dislocation movement were the major deformation mechanisms for the 8090/SiC_p aluminum composite. The predictions resulting from the simple theoretical models were shown to be in consistence with the experimental results.

KEYWORDS: superplasticity, metal matrix composites, deformation mechanisms

INTRODUCTION

In the last decade, discontinuously reinforced aluminium based metal matrix composites (MMCs) have been successfully manufactured through powder metallurgy technology. These high performance MMCs are attractive for many structural applications because of their high specific strength and modulus of elasticity. These composites, however, have lower ductility when compared with their monolithic alloys. In recent years, some aluminium-based MMCs of fine equiaxed grained structure were found to be able to behave superplasticity under the conditions of high strain rates and high testing temperatures [1-7]. These findings are important since one of the major drawbacks of conventional superplastic forming technology is that the forming rate is too low. The discovery of superplastic behaviour of some aluminium-based MMCs at high-strain-rates, thus makes these materials to be even more attractive to industry.

There are two common types of commercially available discontinuous reinforced MMCs, i.e. whisker and particulate reinforced composites. Both of them have been observed to behave superplastically. Although there are many investigations on high-strain-rate superplasticity of MMCs, their deformation mechanisms have not yet been fully understood clearly.

EXPERIMENTAL INVESTIGATIONS

A 20vol. % SiC whisker reinforced 6061 aluminium composite and a 17 vol.% SiC particulate reinforced 8090 aluminium composite were examined and compared in this paper. The composites were manufactured by powder metallurgy, and the material were supplied in sheet form having a thickness of 2mm. For the 6061/SiC_w aluminium composite, the size of the reinforcement was 0.45 ~ 0.65 μm in diameter and 5 ~ 80 μm in length, and its solidus temperature was found to be 857K. Whereas, the average particle size and the solidus temperature of the 8090/SiC_p aluminium composite was about 3 μm and 833K respectively.

The relationship between the total elongation-to-failure and the initial strain rate of the composite at different test temperatures for 6061/SiC_w was shown in Fig.1. A maximum elongation of 440 % was obtained at the strain rate of $1.7 \times 10^{-1} \text{ s}^{-1}$ and at 873 K which is just slightly above the solidus temperature of 6061/SiC_w. Similarly, the relationship between the elongation and the initial strain rate of 8090/SiC_p aluminum composite at different test temperatures was shown in Fig.2. A maximum elongation of 300 % was obtained at the strain rate of $1.8 \times 10^{-1} \text{ s}^{-1}$ and at 848 K which is just slightly above the solidus temperature of 8090/SiC_p.

The change of flow stress at true strain of 0.2 with strain rate of the 6061/SiC_w aluminum composite was shown in Fig. 3. The m value in the range of 10^{-2} to 10^0 s^{-1} was about 0.34. The change of flow stress at true strain of 0.2 with strain rate of 8090/SiC_p aluminum composite was shown in Fig. 4. The m value in the range of 10^{-2} to 10^0 s^{-1} was about 0.37 - 0.53.

Figure 1. Change of elongation with strain rate at different temperatures for 6061/SiC_p aluminum composite. ●873 K; □883 K;▲ 853 K; ○ 833 K; ◆ 813 K.

Figure 2. Change of elongation with strain rate at different temperatures for 8090/SiC_p aluminum composites.

Figure 3. Change of flow stress with strain rate at different temperatures and at true strain = 0.2 for 6061/SiC_p aluminum composite. ○ 813 K; ◆ 833 K; △ 853 K; ● 873 K; □ 883 K.

Figure 4. Change of flow stress with strain rate at different temperatures for 8090/SiC_p aluminum composite.

SUPERPLASTIC DEFORMATION MECHANISMS

The strain rate sensitivity, m , was an important indicator of superplastic deformation mechanism. It was argued that when $m = 0.5$, grain boundary sliding and interfacial sliding accommodated by dislocation movement along the grain boundaries would be the major deformation mechanisms for some fine-grained superplastic aluminum composites [8-11]. On the other hand, solute-drag controlled dislocation climb/glide mechanism was considered to be superplastic deformation mechanism for aluminum composites [12] when m is well below 0.5.

In the present study, dislocation climb/glide was assumed to be the major accommodation mechanism for the 6061/SiC_w aluminum composite as m is only 0.34. The constitutive equation [13] for creep under the dislocation climb/glide mechanism could be expressed as:

$$\dot{\epsilon} \approx \beta \gamma^2 (D/b^2)(Gb^3/kT)(\sigma/G)^3 \quad (1)$$

where β was a dimensionless constant, γ was a constant, D was the diffusivity, G is shear modulus, T is absolute temperature, b is Burgers vector, k is Boltzmann's constant.

In order to apply this equation to the high-strain-rate superplastic deformation, the glide velocity v_g , should be expressed as $\beta/(D/h^2)(\sigma b^3/kT)$, where h was the climb distance of dislocation. Moreover, the presence of threshold stress, σ_0 , in the high-strain-rate superplastic deformation of aluminum composites should be considered and the equation (1) could be modified as:

$$\dot{\epsilon} = \alpha \frac{Gb^3}{kTh^2} \exp\left(-\frac{Q}{RT}\right) \left(\frac{\sigma - \sigma_o}{G}\right)^3 \quad (2)$$

where α was a constant whose value depended on microstructural factors and Q was the activation energy of superplastic deformation. The experimental result for the temperature of 853 K which was slightly below the solidus temperature was used to determine the constant α . At this temperature, the threshold stress was 1.2 MPa and the true strain rate was $1.4 \times 10^{-1} \text{ s}^{-1}$ at the flow stress of 5.85 MPa. If h was assumed to be $12b$ [14], α was calculated to be about 6.8462×10^3 . In order to compare the predicted strain rate with the experimental results, the strain rate at the optimum temperature of 873 K which was slightly higher than the solidus temperature was predicted using the equation (2). At this temperature, the threshold stress was 0.22 MPa. If h was assumed to be $5b$ [15], the constitutive relationships relating strain rate and flow stress for the 6061 aluminium composite at the optimum temperature of 873 K is hence given as follows.

$$\dot{\epsilon} = 1.3762 \times 10^{-2} (\sigma - 0.22)^3. \quad (3)$$

For the 8090 aluminium composite, since a relatively high m value of 0.37~0.53 was found in the high-strain-rate range, grain boundary sliding and interfacial sliding accommodated by dislocation movement along the grain boundaries would be the major deformation mechanisms. Recently, the authors have developed a model to predict the high-strain-rate superplastic deformation of aluminium composites based on the deformation mechanisms of grain boundary sliding and interfacial sliding [10]. According to their model, the constitutive equation which describing the stress-strain relationship of superplastic particulate reinforced composite deformed at temperatures slightly above its solidus temperature is expressed as:

$$\dot{\epsilon}_t = \frac{1}{75\sqrt{3}} \left[\left(1 - \frac{1}{p}\right) b D_I + \frac{1}{f} (2p - 1) b D_{GB} \right] \frac{(\sigma - \sigma_o)^2}{kTG} \quad (4)$$

where D_I is interfacial diffusivity, D_{GB} is grain boundary diffusivity, p is the ratio of the matrix grain size to the particle size of the reinforcement and $f = [\pi / (3\sqrt{2} v_r)]^{1/3}$ where v_r is the volume fraction of reinforcement. At the optimum temperature of 848K, the constitutive equation is obtained as follows.

$$\dot{\epsilon} = 3.292 \times 10^{-3} (\sigma - 0.5)^2. \quad (5)$$

Figure 5 shows the comparison between the theoretical prediction and the experimental findings for the composites. The predictions are in consistence with the experimental findings. However, it should be pointed out that the constitutive equation for the 6061 aluminium doesn't take the shape and size of the grain and whiskers into consideration. Moreover the assumed climb distance used in this equation is not so accurate. A more precise model for superplastic whisker reinforced aluminum composites should be worthwhile to develop.

Figure 5. Comparison of the theoretical predictions (\circ 6061/SiC_w; Δ 8090/SiC_p) with experimental findings (\bullet 6061/SiC_w; \blacktriangle 8090/SiC_p).

CONCLUSIONS

High-strain-rate superplasticity of 6061/SiC_w and 8090/SiC_p aluminum composite was investigated and compared. A maximum elongation of 440 % was obtained for the 6061/SiC_w aluminum composite and a maximum elongation of 300 % was obtained for the 8090/SiC_p aluminum composite. The strain rate sensitivity, m , was found to be about 0.34 for 6061/SiC_w and about 0.5 for 8090/SiC_p aluminum composite. Dislocation climb/glide was considered to be the major accommodation mechanism for the 6061/SiC_w aluminum composites and grain boundary sliding and interfacial sliding accommodated by dislocation movement was the major deformation mechanisms for the 8090/SiC_p aluminum composite. The predictions resulting from the simple theoretical models were shown to be in reasonable agreements with the experimental results. However, a more precise model for superplastic whisker reinforced aluminum composites with consideration of whisker size and shape is particularly worthwhile to develop.

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